

Thoughts on the Origin of Mass

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Part 1: What is going on with EMR.

As an amateur physicist I make no claim to be a great mathematician or have access to enormous facilities, but I do have a long and consuming interest in particle Physics. I have studied this subject from many angles with an accent more on the “how” than the “what”. This study has led me to answer some of my own questions and some of those answers, I believe, are unique and revealing. In this paper I try to explain my thoughts and give you, the reader, I hope, some serious food for thought and perhaps encouragement to use these ideas in some further research.

I began my journey of exploration when I tried to understand the “how” of Einstein’s famous $E=mc^2$ equation. It was clear to me that this meant that matter and energy are two forms of the same thing, that no matter can exist unless it is structured out of particles of energy. As simple as this fact is, it is hard to accept but accept it we must. Taken another way, perhaps we should say: **“Elementary particles of matter are indivisible particles of energy which appear and act as matter with the property of mass.”**

To begin to understand the implications of this concept we need to begin with the simplest and purest form of energy, Electromagnetic Radiation or EMR.

In 1850 Maxwell famously described EMR waves as oscillation of electric and magnetic fields. Now an electric field is defined as “an electric property associated with each point in the space where a single or many charge/s is/are present” and an oscillation of those charges means they swing back and forth from positive to negative. We also know that magnetism exists only when a moving or changing charge is present. So the picture in all the textbooks show EMR as an electric wave oscillating from positive to negative while at right angles to it is the magnetic wave which swings polarity in phase with it.

The Interesting thing about the Maxwell model is that it depends on the energy moving. For the model to work the electric field must oscillate causing the magnetic field to swing polarity, which itself causes the next swing in the charge, and the energy goes along for the ride itself depending on and at the same time driving the magnitude of the fields themselves.

However, there is a problem with EMR. We know from work by Einstein and others it has both “wave” and “particle” characteristics. The exact mechanism of the transmission of these waves is not fully understood but the evidence that they are “quantized” is irrefutable. The individual quanta do not appear to be necessarily linked to each other as many lab experiments with very low intensity radiation and observations of distant astronomic objects have demonstrated the reception of individual quanta of energy arriving on occasions spaced apart by seconds or even longer. They have also shown irrefutably that those quanta of energy are of a unique magnitude linked specifically to the frequency of the wave with the energy growing larger as the frequency is higher.

The only variables affecting energy E in this picture are frequency and the electric field, and the only variable in the latter can be the density (or size) of charge q in that field, so we can say:

As E increases, ω increases and q increases or mathematically

$$E \propto f(\omega) \propto f(q)$$

Equ. 1.1

To determine the nature of those functions we go first the famous Feynman equation² which finds that the energy of an electron is given by $U_{elec} = \frac{q^2}{8\pi a \epsilon_0}$ where all items on the denominator are constants for this purpose, so that they can be replaced by a single constant k.

In my own work I derived an expression of similar form but with different constants³, but it too related the energy E to the square of q . We also know that the relationship between E and ω is given by Planck's equation⁴ as $E = h \omega$. So we can rewrite Equ. 1.1 as:

$$E = h\omega = \frac{q^2}{k} \quad \text{Equ. 1.2}$$

Moving to the alternative form of energy, namely mass, let us add Einstein's equation into the mix to get:

$$E = h\omega = \frac{q^2}{k} = mc^2 \quad \text{Equ. 1.3}$$

Written another way, $\pm q = \sqrt{h\omega \cdot k} = \sqrt{km} \cdot c = \sqrt{Ek}$. Equ. 1.4

The constant k can be evaluated by substituting the properties of an electron but as, for the purpose of this analysis, we are interested only in relative relationships, we can say:

$$\left[\frac{q_1}{q_2} \right] = \sqrt{\frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2}} = \sqrt{\frac{m_1}{m_2}} = \sqrt{\frac{E_1}{E_2}} \quad \text{Equ. 1.5}$$

The equation makes it clear that the sign of the charge is irrelevant, only it's magnitude is important.

So what is this thing we call "charge". In the macro world of matter, the answer is easy, it is the presence of a surplus of electrons for negative, and a deficit of them for positive. In space in EMR or in the micro world there are no electrons, so the real answer is we really don't know, and because we really don't know what a "charge" is, it is not possible to determine the size or number of individual charges that make up the "density" of the electric field that oscillates, and we certainly don't know how many charges of what size makes up the total charge of a single quantum. However, if we want to really understand what is going on we need to bring it all down to that individual quantum where it must mean that it is the oscillation of a single charge or small group of charges that equal the size of that charge and the resulting magnetic effects that oscillation must cause to sustain the quantum on its travels.

To further understand this question, let's look at the point we know that energy and matter are equivalent, the "creation" of an electron positron pair. In our natural world the simplest form of matter is an electron and it's charge mate a positron. The sparking of these particles shows that they can also act as waves and indeed can experimentally be shown to be able to switch backwards and forwards between the two forms. High energy gamma waves under the right circumstances spark off an electron positron pair and if these entities recollide they disappear again and release gamma rays of equal total energy. This fact is a clear confirmation of the equivalence of the two forms of energy.

To look in some more detail at the process of conversion of these high energy gamma rays into electron positron pair we find there is nothing new in this information, it is available from many sources. Gamma rays are high frequency high energy electromagnetic radiation (EMR). Clearly to produce a pair of particles, the energy of the gamma rays must be greater than the sum of the energies of the two particles. We know the rest energy of each of an electron and a positron is $0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ so the energy of the Gamma rays must be greater than $1.022 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ from which we can deduce from Planck's law will have a frequency of greater than $2.47 \times 10^{20} \text{ Hz}$. If such a ray were to pass close to a nucleus a pair of particles a positron and an electron are sparked off. If the two were to subsequently collide they would reverse the process and produce two identical gamma rays of total energy equal to $1.022 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ confirming that the energy of the gamma ray has indeed been converted into these two

particles of matter and converted back again into two quanta of gamma radiation, but of necessity, each half the energy and frequency. Exactly what happens in the process of particle sparking is still not at all clear but the net effect is that if the energy and frequency (and by deduction, charge) of a quantum of EMR is greater than the level of 1.022MeV then certain circumstances can cause the spinning off of the negative half of the electric field to form the electron while the spinning off of the positive half forms the positron.

In the previous paragraph I used the word "Converted". Perhaps if we used the word "Transformed" it would make it more clear that the two particles are still quanta of energy, now in the form of matter with the property of mass. In EMR it is clearly energy, in matter it still is energy now in the form of matter. Taking this view, it makes nonsense of the controversy as to whether a photon has mass. The word "photon" is simply an easy way of describing a "quantum of EMR" and as such it is energy which is at the same time mass in alternative form.

It is interesting to note that the transformation described above is always precisely into a positron and an electron, it is never either two positrons or two electrons or indeed any other elementary "particle". The other interesting fact is that the two appear together, not one after another. In fact, the conversion must be instantaneous, so if the quantum contained a multitude of charges that all swung back and forth in unison from positive to negative, then at the instant of conversion all the charges in the quantum must be one or the other and the production of both a particle with a positive charge and one with a negative charge would not be possible: it would have to be one or the other! This must mean that the positive side of the EMR wave must exist concurrently with the negative side meaning that EMR actually must be both charges rising and falling at the same time in phase with each other.

This may be difficult to visualize. I like to use the simulation of a ball of energy moving through empty space. As it does so it forces space to part as it passes through, causing space to become charged. Because of charge parity, the two sides of the split must be positive and negative of equal magnitude, that magnitude depending on the magnitude of the energy ball. Once the energy ball has passed the charges collapse and neutralize each other. Now replace the energy ball with a quantum of energy and you got it about right. Yes, you got it about right but you have also created the conundrum that puzzles us all. The magnitude of charge depends on the quantity of energy in the quantum, and that quantity of energy depends on the movement of the charge within the magnetic field which is itself created by the movement of that same charge.

However, this new model allows the charges to be always in balance, an equal number of positive charges as there are negative charges. As stated earlier, we don't know if the charge of a quantum of EMR is a single point charge or a group of lesser charges that total to the magnitude of charge required, but logic would suggest that it is probably the former. Consider sunlight for example, it is made up of radiation of all frequencies and energies from low energy infra red through visible light to the ultra violet range and beyond, and yet individual quanta applicable to each and all those energies and frequencies coexist without interference. If the quanta were to be created by multiple charges as opposed to a single point charge, it would be impossible to separate one quantum from another in the stream. This strongly suggests that the actual mechanism is that each quantum of each individual frequency of the EMR is indeed a single matching pair of a positive and negative charge which remain linked to each other and only each other. **Indeed it seems that this is a property of the quantization of EMR - each point charge pair is uniquely associated with a specific energy amount to define a quantum.** The magnitude of the charge is not linear, double the energy only increases the charge by a factor of 1.414.

The conclusion I make from all this is that every quantum in an EMR energy wave has three significant variables namely energy, frequency, and charge and these three variables are related and unique to each combination and it is that uniqueness which defines the properties of the quantum.

An equally important conclusion is that if the relationship between those three variables in the EMR "wave" which is parent to the spawned "particles" is defined by the energy, then the three variables must be similarly

related in those progeny particles. The two particles spawned each have half the energy of the wave from which they spawned and when they collide they produce not one quantum but two with energies now equal to that of each particle or half of that of the quantum in the original wave.

The above being true means that if that unique relationship is not present in a particle, one must conclude that the particle is not elementary and must be a combination of particles that do meet that criteria, because, very simply, there is no way they can form unless they do. This means also that a particle or indeed matter itself cannot exist without charge, and any particle that is neutral must have charge that is balanced positive and negative together.

The validity of this statement is critical to the understanding of elementary particles. **It says that every elementary particle must have a charge which increases proportionally to the square root of the energy, In other words a particle without charge is not elementary and must be a combination of at least two elementary particles with opposite charges.** As troublesome as this statement is, it is vital that a mechanism for how this can be must be found.

Another key conclusion this expression leads to is that it is impossible to differentiate between the energy related to a positive charge and that related to a negative charge, which while unsurprising in a mathematical context but may be critical in understanding the structure of matter. **The energy and mass in a positron is in every way identical to the energy and mass in an electron albeit their opposite charges. There is nothing anti about a positron.**

So a positron is not *Anti*-matter, it is simply matter transformed from the energy of a positive charge as an electron is matter transformed from the energy of a negative charge and other than the charge, the properties of that matter is identical. And perhaps this is why we don't know where all the anti-matter in the universe is, because there isn't any, it's just all plain matter, and we cannot tell the difference.

Another conclusion could be that perhaps there are in fact only two elementary particles – The electron and the positron. All matter can be a combination of those two entities if only they could coexist.

Perhaps we need to understand how negative charged matter particles can coexist with positive charged matter particles to find the answer, and perhaps the neutrino is that solution. In part 2 we will examine that possibility.

And in the end Einstein was only partly right, his equation should actually be $E \rightleftharpoons mc^2$

References

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